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LANGUAGE CULTURE AS A COMPONENT OF THE INTERNATIONAL RELATIONS SPECIALISTS TRAINING: ORIGINS AND PRESENT

The purpose of the work is to state the speech culture role in the training of the international sphere of activity specialists as an instrument of interaction with different cultures while performing their professional duties. **The methodology of the study** is to use such research methods as study, analyses and generalization in order to reveal the notion of speech culture, namely, diplomatic eloquence as the ability to choose and exercise speech act (speech behaviour) depending on the professional speech' goals and content through linguistic means, as well addressing to the strategy and tactics of communication. **The scientific novelty** is to describe the problem of mastering the diplomatic eloquence skills as an act of a cultural dialogue implementation in the international experts' professional activity. The problems of communication, discourse, and various professional skills formation of specialists from various fields have widely been discussed in the scientific literature, but the problem of diplomatic communication and the speech culture formation skills in the context of professional international activity remains to be studied. **Conclusions.** Language is not merely a means of diplomatic communication, but rather a tool for expanding diplomatic sphere of activity. Since every language is deeply rooted in a certain culture, it is a unique representation of the world picture. However, the cultural dialogue, implemented through eloquence between different countries, requires the existence of complex multidimensional

processes. Thus, diplomatic negotiations, even held in the same language, sometimes do not reach the positive result because of the impossibility and inability to convey the message content.

Key words: speech culture; diplomatic eloquence; diplomatic discourse; communicative personality; diplomatic communications; professional activity.

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Мовна культура як складова підготовки фахівців-міжнародників: витоки і сьогодення

Мета роботи – з'ясувати роль мовної культури в підготовці фахівців міжнародної сфери діяльності як інструменту взаємодії з різними культурами під час виконання своїх професійних обов'язків. **Методологія дослідження** полягає у використанні таких методів дослідження як вивчення, аналіз та узагальнення з метою розкриття поняття мовної культури, а саме дипломатичного красномовства як здатність вибирати й здійснювати мовну дію (поведінку) залежно від цілей і змісту професійного мовлення за допомогою мовних засобів, а також за допомогою володіння стратегією й тактикою спілкування. **Наукова новизна** полягає в описі проблеми опанування навичками дипломатичного красномовства як акту реалізації культурного діалогу в професійній діяльності фахівців-міжнародників. У науковій літературі досить широко висвітлені проблеми спілкування, дискурсу, формування різних професійних умінь фахівців з різних галузей, але при цьому недостатньо вивченою залишається проблема дипломатичної комунікації й формування елементів мовної культури в контексті професійної міжнародної діяльності. **Висновки.** Мова виступає не просто засобом дипломатичного спілкування, а саме інструментом розширення можливостей дипломатичної діяльності. Так як кожна мова є глибоко вкоріненою в певній культурі, то вона є унікальним уявленням про картину світу. Проте культурний діалог, який реалізується завдяки навичкам красномовства і відбувається між країнами, передбачає наявність складних багатовимірних процесів. Дипломатичні перемовини, навіть якщо проводяться однією й тією ж самою мовою, інколи не досягають позитивного результату дипломатичних перемовин через неможливість і невміння донести зміст повідомлення.

Ключові слова: мовна культура; дипломатичне красномовство; дипломатичний дискурс; комунікативні особистості; дипломатичні комунікації; професійна діяльність.

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Речевая культура как составляющая подготовки специалистов-международников: истоки и настоящее

Цель работы – определить роль речевой культуры в подготовке специалистов международной сферы деятельности, как инструмента

взаимодействия с различными культурами во время выполнения своих профессиональных обязанностей. **Методология исследования** заключается в использовании таких методов исследования как изучение, анализ и обобщение с целью раскрытия понятия речевой культуры, а именно дипломатического красноречия как способности выбирать и осуществлять речевое действие (поведение) в зависимости от целей и содержания профессиональной речи с помощью языковых средств, а также с помощью владения стратегией и тактикой общения. **Научная новизна** заключается в описании проблемы освоения навыками дипломатического красноречия как акта реализации культурного диалога в профессиональной деятельности специалистов-международников. В научной литературе достаточно широко освещены проблемы общения, дискурса, формирования различных профессиональных умений специалистов из разных областей, но при этом недостаточно изученной остается проблема дипломатической коммуникации и формирования элементов языковой культуры в контексте профессиональной международной деятельности. **Выводы.** Язык выступает не просто средством дипломатического общения, а именно инструментом расширения возможностей дипломатической деятельности. Так как каждый язык глубоко укоренился в определенной культуре, то он представляет собой уникальное представление о картине мира. Однако культурный диалог, который реализуется благодаря навыкам красноречия и происходит между странами, предполагает наличие сложных многомерных процессов. Дипломатические переговоры, даже если проводятся на одном и том же языке, иногда не достигают положительного результата дипломатических переговоров из-за невозможности и неумения донести смысл сообщения.

Ключевые слова: речевая культура; дипломатическое красноречие; дипломатический дискурс; коммуникативные личности; дипломатические коммуникации, профессиональная деятельность.

Introduction. Diplomacy deals with diverse cultural groups through interaction and negotiation. Its own cultural program forms the negotiations style of each participant. Since different cultural groups communicate in different ways, the culture of the negotiating party influences its style of negotiation.

Political and international activity has always played a special role in the life of society. A certain political position or situation influences upon the country's place in the international arena, its relations with other states, and its role in the world community activities. However, the way the state political leaders present this state plays an important role in determining the country's image. Through well-organized speeches politicians have the opportunity to address both the international community and the citizens of their country.

Recent academic and practical studies do not look into the relationship between diplomacy and culture, especially speech culture, with the comprehension of cultural competence and intercultural exchanges uniting societies and promoting further intercultural interaction. Nowadays discussions are focused exclusively on the existence of cultural communities and common values shared by all cultures. However, the decisive

similarity between cultures should be a secondary one to understanding cultural differences as a logical starting point for the intercultural communities' assessment.

Analysis of previous studies and publications. Diplomacy has always been and remains quite a closed, "quiet" area of intercultural communication, with the purpose being a search for compromise solutions. This feature explains a small number of works devoted, in particular, to the linguistic aspects of diplomatic eloquence and diplomatic communication in general.

Nevertheless, culture of diplomatic speech, in particular, its correctness, accuracy, knowledge of the basics of rhetoric and theory of argumentation, plays a vital role as it being a tool for expanding diplomatic sphere of activity. Using the basic principles and rules of the diplomatic rhetoric – the science of eloquence, an experienced negotiator draws attention to the basic principles of speech influence and the most important communication effects, which make it possible to multiply the effectiveness of spoken words that is especially important in terms of intercultural communication (Vasilenko, 2011, p. 56).

The study of the diplomatic speech culture specifics used in the diplomatic sphere, as well as the description of different aspects of the diplomatic substyle, have a certain value for modern linguistics, cultural studies, and international relations. Of undoubted interest are some works, researching and describing diplomatic substyle with reference to different languages and cultures. There is also a number of special works related to the issues of arranging diplomatic documents in various languages, problems of diplomatic etiquette or protocol been written by specialists in the field of international relations and the international economy.

Such linguistic aspects of diplomatic speech as: diplomatic speech functional and stylistic analysis; functional and structural peculiarities of diplomatic correspondence texts; linguistic and pragmatic means of expression of evasion in contemporary political discourse; peculiarities of the diplomatic documents creation and functioning; linguistic aspects of persuasiveness in diplomatic discourse; communicative and pragmatic features of diplomatic discourse; semantic and semiotic aspects of the diplomatic discourse; as well as an intensive structure of the diplomatic discourse were studied by such contemporary researchers as O. M. Matsko, O. M. Pazynych, O. V. Ponomarenko, T. I. Shynkarenko, V. B. Skriabina, L. Bostanjan, M. V. Beliakov, and L. M. Terentiy (Matsko, 2001; Pazynych, 2001; Ponomarenko, 2004; Shynkarenko, 2009; Skriabina, 2018; Bostandzhjan, 2015; Beljakov, 2011; Terentij, 2016).

Previously unsettled tasks. However, there was no any comprehensive analysis of the diplomatic speech culture specifics and necessity in the training of the international sphere of activity specialists. Thus, the relevance of the study determined by an increased interest of linguistics and specialists in culture studies to the problems of communicative interaction, in particular, speech culture in its close connection with human practice, thus raising a necessity in an integrated approach to analyse a diplomatic eloquence as a primarily tool of the diplomatic communication.

The purpose of the article. Challenges of the modern world condition the relevance of the study of the relationship between diplomatic processes and cultural variations. Whether there is a common professional speech culture in diplomacy other than national one; how it affects diplomacy; to what extent the culture of diplomatic eloquence is helpful in excuting proffesional activity.

Presenting main material. Nowadays it has become apparent that an individual's professional competence is impossible without possessing special knowledge of speech culture and the ability to participate in professional speech communication. However, despite there are many works devoted to the study of deliberative eloquence of private rhetoric, diplomatic rhetoric has not yet been studied enough. Knowing the Ukrainian diplomatic rhetoric history allows us to understand the essence and content of the modern diplomatic eloquence deeper. In this regard, it is necessary to study its sources and identify the diplomatic rhetoric's characteristic features of the different periods of its existence.

Diplomatic eloquence has several types of speeches, among which there are (Matsko, 2006, p. 203):

- speeches at international and interstate conferences, gatherings, and meetings;
- speeches during diplomatic acts (agreements, contacts, communiqués);
- speeches during visits, social functions, farewells, awardings, etc.;
- diplomatic correspondence.

Diplomatic eloquence requires an unimpeachable possession both his native literary and foreign languages, a good pronunciation, a developed sense of language, the ability to join the desired topics, ideas, thoughts, to be able to communicate, be tactful and correct. Diplomatic eloquence belongs to a particularly sophisticated form; it is an elitist, higher level of speech and must be specially studied as a means of professional diplomatic skill.

The origins of the diplomatic eloquence can be traced back to ancient rhetoric. It was necessary to be a good speaker, to possess communication skills to succeed in negotiations with representatives of other countries. Brilliant speakers of the ancient times often became ambassadors of their countries and sought significant success in the international arena. For centuries, international sphere has developed certain rules and standards of diplomatic communication. The international actors should strictly follow them in diplomatic communication, both oral and written, as these rules aimed at the intergovernmental communication processes support. Thus, the art of persuasion has long been the foundation of diplomacy, since it involved the establishment of contacts and mutual understanding in the negotiation process. (Skriabina, 2018, p. 268).

Depending on historical period, diplomacy (as the art of negotiation) had special external (formal) and internal (substantial) sides, which laid the basis for a certain historical tradition to be formed.

According to A. N. Sakharov the first information about the diplomatic practice of the Eastern Slavs' ancestors can be found in the chronicle sources of the VI – early VII centuries. He states that the Antes conducted negotiations with their neighbors on territorial issues, exercised the embassy exchanges, concluded military alliance treaties, agreements on the redemption of prisoners, etc. (Saharov, 1986, p. 34).

During the times of Kyiv Rus, diplomatic relations with other states began to be established from the IX century. As it was the time of the Slavic tribes' clash with the Byzantine Empire, the Greeks played a main role as they had already developed writing and formed the main genres of the diplomatic communication.

Until the XII century there were no clearly marked boundaries of Kyiv Rus, it resulted in various functions of the ancient Rus diplomacy to be outlined as in relation to neighboring small nations not having their own statehood, as in relation to already established states. Diplomats addressed mainly to such oral genres of diplomatic rhetoric

as negotiations and final speeches; as for the written genres, agreement, diplomas, and private letter were mostly used (Pashuto, 1968, p. 26).

The Old Rus Embassy Service had already been founded by IX–X centuries. The diplomat's authority depended not only on the political position of the state; he represented, but largely depended on his personal qualities. With Baptism of Kyiv Rus, the diplomatic service widely used clergymen, well known for their literacy (Saharov, 1986, p. 41). The negotiation process in the Rus diplomatic practice developed gradually. As a rule, negotiations took place at different levels, with the most responsible ones been headed by the Great Princes.

The disintegration of Kyiv Rus into principalities, followed by the time of strife, did not contribute to the diplomatic rhetoric's development of that time. In different principalities, the future ambassadors were trained differently. For example, princes learned languages and literacy from a young age; they attended the embassy receptions and listened to the controversy of their speeches, thus, training and learning all the diplomatic rhetoric subtleties. Trying to solve the problem with very few people been able to speak foreign languages, starting from the XIV century princes began to invite Greeks and Italians to their service. They used the Azov and Taurian Genoese as mediators in relations between Italy and the Northern Rus. Venetians greatly contributed to the spread of many Byzantine diplomatic speech art techniques in Rus (Biletska, 2016, p. 2).

The second half of the XVIIth century was marked with the rhetoric playing an enormous role in the process of international negotiations, most closely associated with the personality of a certain diplomat: his ability to produce texts, to perceive them correctly and organize them accordingly to current situations (Timofeev, 2015, p. 96).

Nowadays, the diplomatic speech culture has its specifics inherent only to it. These features were clearly formulated by M. Zubkov and are the following (Zubkov, 2004, p. 27):

- a neutral tone of message presentation expressed only in direct sense;
- accuracy and clarity combined with conciseness, pithiness, sequence of facts;
- settled speech clusters, high standardization of presentation;
- strict regulation of the text; for a clear organization, the text been divided into paragraphs, paragraphs, sub-paragraphs.

These are the main decisive features in the formation of the speech units system and the methods of their use in the diplomatic eloquence.

O. M. Matsko points out the diplomatic subtext to be distinguished by its traditional genres and linguistic-compositional structures – linguistic formulas with the target directions of the diplomatic sphere: establishing and maintaining contact, searching for direct and indirect ways, exit from predicted and unforeseen situations, etc. The researcher states the etiquette to be one of the most important signs of the diplomatic speech, characterized by a general tone of respect, attention, benevolence towards the addressee, caution, correctness and tolerance of communication (Matsko, 2001, p. 12).

The diplomatic correspondence is a most indicative type of diplomatic speech genres as it shows the most complete features of diplomatic speech culture implementation (Pazynych, 2001, p. 8).

Diplomatic activity is bilateral (on the one hand, it is drawn to the middle of the country, and on the other to the outside world), therefore, the culture of diplomatic

broadcasting is characterized by significant political and social constraints or even a taboo. A diplomat in all communicative situations should be especially vigilant about his speech. Increased self-control of the speaker in all communicative situations, high level of professional work and social culture of the interlocutors is another important feature of the diplomatic subtext of the official-business style of speech.

Today, there are some types of the diplomatic speech culture oral genres, traced deeply to antiquity (Kalinina, 2017):

- diplomatic negotiations and consultation;
- diplomatic conversation;
- closed diplomatic conversation;
- speeches at the meeting in a narrow format;
- speeches at the official diplomatic conferences;
- “gentlemen’s agreement” (purely diplomatic negotiation genre — the oral form of an international treaty, as a rule, is subject to written clearance in the future);
- speeches at the dinner, at the reception, at the dinner-reception, at the signing of the contract, welcoming speech;
- government statements, statements on the results of the negotiations;
- joint statements;
- speeches or demarches (an emergency statement by the foreign affairs agencies of one state about another);
- speeches by diplomats at a press conference;
- verbal note;
- reports of the Information and Press Department of the Ministry of Foreign Affairs;
- communique.

Conclusions. The culture of diplomatic speech is a specific phenomenon, the features of which not being similar to the features of other types of rhetoric. The basis of a diplomat’s speech is a state interest and certain historical realities, due to which the speaker builds his speech. In the current conditions of globalization, when members of the international community observe the diplomatic negotiations, it is very important to keep to general human moral and ethical principles, otherwise this may result in social and cultural isolation, seriously harm the entire foreign policy of the state.

Analyzing the peculiarities of the diplomats’ individual speech culture, it is possible to build a kind of ideal behavior model and speech strategy in international negotiations. The combination of such ideal models is reflected in the rules of the international communication maintenance aimed at avoiding misunderstandings in the compilation of a conceptual series of a specific diplomatic speech. The main task of the diplomatic rhetorical principle is to organise presentation of the diplomat’s thoughts to be heard and understood by others, to achieve certain goals through the skillful realization of his speech plot, thus forecasting the future course of events and preventing unpleasant situations that run counter to the interests of the country.

In its turn, the combination of speech formulas and clichés, politeness (in all possible variants) forms a system of speech etiquette for each nation, and not only in the field of diplomacy. The role of speech culture in the overall development of diplomatic communication, as well as the role of rhetoric in the general development of diplomatic communication should be taken into account. This provides a further basis

for the new rhetorical discoveries in individual diplomats' activity, a potential basis for the creation of regular new rules for conducting international negotiations.

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РОЗВИТОК НАЦІОНАЛЬНО-ОРІЄНТОВАНИХ ВИДІВ ТУРИЗМУ В ЕПОХУ ГЛОБАЛІЗАЦІЇ

Метою роботи є обґрунтування необхідності розвитку національно-орієнтованих видів туризму в епоху глобалізації. **Методологія дослідження** передбачає проведення аналізу основних дефініцій теоретичної бази національно-орієнтованих видів туризму, систематизацію відповідного кола споріднених видів туризму та визначення основних засад формування національно-орієнтованих видів туризму. **Наукова новизна.** Введено до наукового обігу теорії туризмознавства та обґрунтовано поняття «національно-орієнтовані види туризму». **Висновки.** Визначено культурологічний зміст та форми національно-орієнтованих видів туризму, охарактеризовано вплив етнокультурного потенціалу території на розвиток туризму, обґрунтовано необхідність розвитку національно-орієнтованих видів туризму в епоху глобалізації.